

EDUCATIONAL POTENTIAL OF MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES AS A DIDACTIC MEANS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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1. Introduction

Teaching foreign language is complicated process in which the construction of an artificial language environment for students in the absence of a natural one necessitates the most flexible and extensive application of various technological teaching methods. As a result, new multimedia opportunities have been put to the most varied use in the teaching of a foreign language. Lighting and sound engineering gadgets were typically employed in the process of learning foreign languages in modern institutions. However, new information technologies have now made their way into the classroom: a computer, a multimedia textbook, the Internet, and an electronic instructional resource. The usage of these new information technologies makes it possible to improve the effectiveness of teaching and the skills of everyday and professional communication of learners. Besides, in modern methods of teaching foreign languages, the usage of multimedia technologies plays a significant role, as multimedia is an interactive system that provides simultaneous work with sound, animated computer graphics, video frames, static images and text. A. Frigaard (2002) and M. Timuçin (2006) confirmed that multimedia technology increases the development of teaching methods and learners' knowledge. Y. Lam and G. Lawrence (2002) also expressed that technology helps learners to regulate their own learning process and have access to any information that their teachers cannot provide. This research project will provide an overview of multimedia technologies as a didactic tool for teaching a foreign language.

2. Problem Statement.

In last two decades, foreign language teaching system showed incredible changes on that proved the effectiveness of using the modern technologies in the training of foreign and second language students. The scientists developed variants of using modern technologies in foreign language teaching and recommended several programs that can serve as a basis for the development of teaching a foreign language from their experience. Many teaching projects, however, continue to be plagued by delays and cost overruns, which are typically related to insufficient language instruction. First, the existing system of professional training of future teachers of foreign languages is not capable to provide formation of professional competences, which meet new requirements. Second, the training of future specialists should in the field of foreign languages at the University, so that they can continue to work competently with information and effectively use, as well as be able to develop multimedia technologies in their activities. In summary, there is a need for a better understanding of the effectiveness of multimedia technologies as a didactic means of teaching a foreign language and using it appropriately and productively. The following research questions must be addressed in further detail:

1. How to use the multimedia programs which are used in the education process?

2. What should teachers do in order to understand the individual didactic multimedia capabilities of students?
3. What are the didactic principles of multimedia in usage?
4. What are the effective way of the using multimedia as a didactic education environment?

3. Objectives

The long-term goal of the research is to develop a program for teaching future foreign language teachers using multimedia technologies. These are not only new technical means but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the learning process. Particularly, the study has the following sub-objectives:

1. To provide a comprehensive review of sources and characteristics of multimedia technologies;
2. To develop multimedia technologies as a didactic means of teaching a foreign language;
3. To review current industry practices and researches in regards to teaching a foreign language;

The result of this study will be valuable to children to accelerate foreign language dynamically with the help of didactic materials.

4. Preliminary Literature Review

A preliminary literature review shows that didactics as a theory of learning and education is rooted in the depths of centuries. Training was always there when a person existed. The theory of learning began to form already when there was a meaningful need to pass on the accumulated achievements to the descendants. Didactics is a special part of pedagogy, which in modern times acquires special features and characteristics of an independent science. The processes of education and training, closely related to upbringing, are not only the subject of didactics, but are also an organic part of upbringing. Everyone knows that our society is worried and takes care that the previously accumulated experience, as well as skills, abilities and knowledge, are also well included and mastered by the generations entering a new life. Learning and education serves this sole purpose. This very goal is the assimilation of the previously studied experience by our ancestors by the descendants. But at all stages of the historical development of didactics, its task was and still remains to determine the content of education of new generations, as well as to find new ways of equipping descendants with skills, knowledge and skills and to reveal the laws of this process. That is why didactics is defined as a theory of learning and education. But everyone knows that the learning process is always inextricably linked with education, not only moral, but also mental. And, given this factor, there are solid grounds for defining didactics as a theory of learning and education, as well as upbringing. This, first of all, includes the formation of the students' worldview. The process of teaching and education is currently the subject of didactics at the present stage of development. This means the content of education, which is implemented in curricula, textbooks, programs, as well as the means and methods of teaching, the educational role of the entire educational process, organizational forms of education and conditions that favor

the creative and active work of students, as well as their mental and physical development [A.R. Masalimova, "Teaching Theory", Kazan 2018, p19].

5. Methodology

The primary research method for this study is literature review and personality-oriented. In personality-oriented (learning-centered approach) the center is the personality of the student and his cognitive activity, and the students' needs are the basis for the construction of the course. Analysis of specialized literature on research topics as well as of training programs of a foreign language for pupils was conducted. A system of classes for pupils of a foreign language for a semester in foreign language teaching and for teachers a number of recommendations for creating a course and conducting classes using multimedia technologies has been developed. Besides, there were several searching that prove the effectiveness of multimedia techniques in language learning.

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